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Assessing the Influence of Motor-Generator Device Based Instruction on Students' Motivation in Energy among North-West Colleges of Education, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research investigated the influence of Fabricated Motor Generator Device based instructions on students Motivation, in Energy among colleges of education students in North-West, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi – experimental research design. The population of the study comprised of all Nigeria Certificate in Education 1 students of 2024/2025 academic session. The sample was made up of 100 N.C.E.1 students of colleges of Education from North-West geopolitical zone, Nigeria. Two research questions were answered in the study. The research instrument used was Motivation psychometric test adopted from Bin Dayel, 2018 for data collection with little modification. Motivation psychometric test was validated by three experts to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.85 using test retest reliability method. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Result obtained from the study revealed that students that were taught Energy Concepts using fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instructions are motivated higher than those taught using lecture method with a mean gain of 8.26 against 6.73 and female students are highly motivated with mean gain of 8.73 than the male students with mean gain of 7.94. In conclusion, therefore science teachers are advised to use Motor-Generator Device based instruction in teaching Energy concepts in colleges of educations. Finally, it was recommended that lecturers in colleges of Education should expose their students to Motor-Generator based instructions and that male students should be given more attention as female students are motivated higher than male students.

Keywords: Motor-Generator, Device, Based, Instruction, motivation, Energy, North-West

Introduction

Teacher education generally, serves as an indispensable tool in the development of human civilization and development. Methods of training the teachers have been constantly evolving and changing due to new technologies and research. Previously, teacher education has predominantly depended on primitive idea and ways where learning is imparted with transfer of information without activities being performed in the classroom. Thus, the modern teacher education system has completely eradicated the space limitation of classroom by encouraging the participation of many students from

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every corner of the world by providing knowledge through digital means. Modern teacher education system has been able to attract variety of students and teachers to participate in a technology-based learning such as the Motor-Generator based learning. Teacher training and development is increasing day by day to ensure quality of education.

Science teacher education refer to the teaching and learning of science to future teachers under training in colleges of education and universities. Many of the developed nations achieved so much in science and technology because of science teacher education. The potential contribution of science and technology to the development of educational objectives is widely recognized as a factor that contributed perhaps more than any other factor to the economic growth of the developed countries as against the developing countries such as Nigeria that do not really embrace the pragmatic adoption of these innovations in their education system. This is why, in most cases, the Nigerian education system seems to be lagging behind among league of nations in terms of digital and technology adoption (Ridwan et, al, 2019). Many Education practitioners and even higher institutions show rather a conservative attitude towards the adoption of technology devices and services, thus the adoption of these innovations seems to be left in the hand of only few. In many of the public schools where technological devices should have its way of influence by dominating the process of teaching and learning, the case is different. This has rendered the discipline of application of technology in the process and learning insignificant. According to Specter, (2019) to think and talk about education without thinking and talking about the technology that could be used to facilitate its processes is almost impossible and it is an easy path to poor educational delivery, especially as it relates to difficult concepts in science.

Difficult concepts are concepts that are not amenable to experience in the classroom or the laboratory. It is sometimes referred to as highly situated or contextualized concept. Babayemi, Akpan and Emah, (2018), identified twenty science concepts perceived to be difficult by the students which are: Habitat and adaptation, uniqueness of man, growth and development, chemicals, work, energy, power, kinetic theory, heat flow, crude oil, evaporation, conduction, petrochemicals, boiling, convection, radiation, change and development, first aid, rescue operations and security. The current Colleges of Education Minimum Standard, 2020 indicated that Energy is an indispensable tool in virtually every aspect of human endeavors. There is hardly any field where Energy is not useful. That is why Energy has been placed as a compulsory course at first level of Nigeria Certificate in Education level I via a course titled Man & Energy (Integrated Science code 123) with the aim of preparing and encouraging intending teachers to learn the concept of energy and create impact in the learners environment, but previous research by different scholars in teacher education revealed that the students understanding of the key basic ideas of energy concept is limited and abstract (Babayemi, Akpan & Emah, 2018, Na Allah & Abdulrahim, 2019). It seems that the reason is how energy is taught in the colleges of Education, therefore developing an instructional resource to teach energy concept is scientifically robust and developmentally appropriate (Ruth & Emmanuel 2020). Despite the importance attached to Energy both as academic discipline and knowledge that everybody used in the society and the effort of government in making Energy a compulsory course at colleges of Education, the performance of students in Energy at the colleges of Education levels in Nigeria is not encouraging. Researchers

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believed that the ineffective teaching strategies were being adopted in the teaching of Energy which led to students' poor performance and retention. They have tested various strategies for the improvement of teaching and learning strategy, which still remains poor. Therefore, it is worthwhile to examine the influence of fabricated Motor-Generator Device base instruction on motivating the students to learn Energy Concept.

Electric Motors and Generators are devices used to change mechanical energy to electrical energy (Generator) and electrical energy to mechanical energy (motors) by electromagnetic means example ceiling fan (Ruth and Emmanuel, 2020). Motor-Generator is a dual function device that changes mechanical energy to electrical energy and vice versa. The device is relatively in expensive and can easily be fabricated from scraps (Sirajo& Yunusa,2022). It also provides a clear and compelling demonstration of Faraday Law of electromagnetic induction and Lorentz Law. Two magnets will be suspended inside two solenoids (coil wire). The solenoid will be connected. Moving one of the magnets induces a current in the solenoids, current flows to the other solenoids where a force is generated to the other magnets causing it to move and produce an effect (Lorentz,1834).

Gender is another factor in this study. There are different findings on gender matters, some in favor of male, others in favor of females and sometimes no gender difference are found. The issue of gender is important in Science Education especially on women empowerment and gender equality. Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioral characteristics differentiating between feminine and masculine (females and males) population (Oludipe, 2022). The importance of examining motivation in relation to gender is based primarily on socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. In view of the expectation that student gender may have impact on their motivation, this was seen in the relationship between gender and academic motivation being examine by substantial body of literature such as Nenty, (2020), Kyei (2021); Awofala (2022), Adeniyi and Nneyi (2022). Agbaye and Alake, (2024). Some of the researchers pointed out that there is no significant gender effect on students' motivation while others found out that there is significant difference in either boys or girls being motivated better. The findings still remain inconclusive and are still being investigated by researchers. There had been a renewed debate on the controversial issue of gender difference on motivation in science. This debate focused on why women are not seeking for carriers in sciences, even though women have made great strides in law, medicine and social sciences professions, very few can be found in graduate programs or profession such as engineering, mathematics and physics, computer science and information technology jobs (Workman and Hyder, 2020). This served as one of the reasons why gender was considered as variable of the research.

Colleges of Educations are saddle with the responsibility of producing qualified teachers at basic level of Education in Nigeria. Although the colleges are oriented to produce teachers, many parents, guardians and husbands does not enroll their children in colleges of education for the of them becoming teachers. The yearning and aspirations for quality and effective teaching delivery have been a long outstanding objective of science teacher education so as to produce future scientist, technologist and engineers for national development.

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The level of motivation of students in colleges of Education have been persistently low over the previous years and report obtained from interview with some colleges of education lecturers teaching the course Man and Energy 1 a one hundred level course indicated that the understanding of the Energy concepts is shallow and abstract. This was supported by the students' performance records of five years (2019-2023) obtained from Federal College of Education (Technical), Gusau Integrated Science Department as follows: 30% in 2019, no student's enrolment in 2020, 35% pass in 2021, 36% in 2023 which is relatively below average.

This negative situation may be caused by poor motivation, lack of proper teaching methodology, misconception of science ideas and concepts as well as poor motivation. Uzoечи & Otuka, (2021) explained that science teachers will be surprised to learn that despite their effort's science students do not grasp the fundamental ideas and concepts taught in the class due poor motivation. Motivation captures students' interest which in turn improves their performance. Adekunle, Samuel & Olubukola, (2024) added that motivation serve as the driving force behind students' engagement, persistence and ultimately their success in science concepts such as Energy. Student face challenges ranging from academic pressure to socio-economic disparities, the role of motivation become more pronounce. A motivated student is more likely to exhibits perseverance in tackling science misconception problems, seek assistance when needed and maintain positive attitude towards learning despite encountering obstacles (Sandra, 2022).

This research aims to address the problem of poor motivation by investigating how hook's model can be used to motivate students, improves their performance and retention in Energy concepts. It will seek to understand the extent to which Motor-Generator Device using hook's model can motivate and enhance learning outcomes.

Objective of the study

The main purpose of the Study is to investigate the influence fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instructions on motivation in energy among colleges of education students in North-West, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to:

- i. Determine the influence of using fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instruction on colleges of education students' motivation in Energy
- ii. Determine the influence of gender on motivation using Motor-Generator Device based instructions

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What are the mean motivation scores of students taught energy concepts using fabricated Motor-Generator as an instructional Device and those taught using lecture method?
- ii. What are the mean motivation scores of male and female students taught energy concepts using fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Methodology

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A quasi -experimental pretest-post -test research design was employed for the study. This means that the design involved two instructional groups: Experimental groups-learning with aid of fabricated Motor – Generator Device based instruction and the control group that learned through conventional approach in colleges of Education (lecture method). The samples for the study were drawn from colleges of education in the North-West geopolitical zone, Nigeria. Multi stage sampling was used to draw the sample. First, the zone was stratified into seven states having two colleges of education each belonging to states and federal governments with exception of Kano which has three. Secondly, the seven states were further stratified into colleges of which one was selected from each state using lucky dip with replacement. Thirdly, the colleges one from each state having equivalent scores in the pretest was selected as sample for the study. Finally, toss of a coin was used to assign two schools as experimental and control groups. The head was assigned as experimental while the tail was assigned as the control groups. Total of 100 participant were used for the study 51 males and 49 females. Energy Psychometric test was adapted from Bin Dayel, 2018 with little modification. The instrument was validated by three experts in science teaching and reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Mean and standard deviations was used to answer the research questions.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What are the mean motivation scores of students taught Energy concepts using fabricated Motor Generator device-based instruction.

The data for answering this research question is provided in Table 1.1

Table 1.1: Mean and Standard Deviation scores of Students Taught Energy Concepts using Motor-Generator Device based instruction.

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	59	16.98	3.52	25.25	2.59	8.26
Control	41	16.87	3.49	21.60	2.36	6.73

Table 1.1, shows mean motivation score and standard deviation score of students taught Energy concepts using the fabricated Motor-Generator device-based instruction and those taught using lecture method, the experimental group had a mean gain score of 8.26 while the control group had mean achievement scores of 6.73.

Research Question 2

How does gender affect the mean motivation scores of students taught Energy concepts using the fabricated Motor Generator device instruction?

The data for answering this research question is provided in Table 1.2

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Table 1.2: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Energy Concepts using Motor Generator Based Instruction.

Group	Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Expt. Group	Male	36	18.47	3.63	26.41	2.46	7.94
	Female	29	17.38	3.33	26.11	2.78	8.73

Table 1.2 shows mean and standard deviation score of male and female students taught Energy concepts using the fabricated Motor-Generator Device and those taught using lecture method. The mean gain motivation score for male was 7.94, while the female students had a mean gain motivation score of 8.73 in the experimental group.

Discussions

The findings of this study were discussed based on the issues raised in the study: Influence of Motor-Generator Device based instructions on students’ motivation in Energy among North-West colleges of Education, Nigeria. The findings reveal that students taught Energy concepts using Fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instructions are motivated higher than those taught using lecture method. This is consistent with the findings of Ruth, (202)and Sirajo ,(2023) who agreed that teaching using learning resources motivate the students.

The findings also revealed that Motor-Generator Device based instructions showed that female students are motivated better than their male counterpart. This is in contrast with the findings of Eriba (2020), Thomas and Igwebuiké, (2022) who reported that male students are motivated than their male counterpart but is in agreement with the findings Godspower and Ihenko (2021).

Conclusion

It is clear from the results obtained above that the use of fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instructions to teach energy concepts on students’ motivation has significant influence. It is therefore concluded that using the device will improve motivation of students to learn energy concept and gender plays an important role where female students are motivated higher than their male counterparts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

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- i. Teachers of science especially in science and technology should expose their students to the use of fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instructions when teaching Energy concepts since it promotes and encourage learning by imitating and learning by doing which at the end enhance performance.
- ii. Teachers should also consider gender as a significant factor in students; motivation, hence special treatment should be given to male students since female students are motivated higher Motor-Generator Device based instructions is used in teaching.

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